

Evaluation of Total Talent Management Phenomena in the Context of Pakistan (Expatriates Perspective)

1st Dr. Sheikh Raheel Manzoor, 2nd Dr. Muhammad Irshad, 3rd Dr. Adil Muhammad,
4th Dr. Khalid Khalil & 5th Mr. Muhammad Salman

¹IBMS, The University of Agriculture, Peshawar, Pakistan

²IBS, Kohat University of Science & Technology, Pakistan

³Abasyn University, Peshawar, Pakistan

⁴IQRA National University, Peshawar, Pakistan

⁵IBS, Kohat University of Science & Technology, Pakistan

* Corresponding author: raheelmanzoor7861@gmail.com

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Abstract: This study was undertaken to evaluate total talent management (TTM) in Pakistan with the aim to explore significant factors responsible for total talent management in Pakistan. The study was quantitative in nature and population comprised of overseas Pakistani pursuing medical and engineering profession in the developed world. The required data was collected through questionnaires and 300 questionnaires were sent to overseas Pakistani engineers and doctors. After segregation of data the same was analyzed through AMOS software. The study analyzed the data via measuring factor analysis, validity and regression analyses achieve study objectives. The statistical findings of this study determine critical factors of total talent management in the context of Pakistan with expatriates prospective. Study emphasis that to ensure total talent management and retain sophisticated number of talented individual to cater the national requirements, government amalgamate with national operated enterprises (NOEs) must focus on a) fair recruitment and selection system, b) provides growth and career development opportunities, c) offering ample pay package, d) adopts fair reward system, ensure a conducive working environment and e) improve living standard via advanced technology.

Keywords: TotalTalent Management, AMOS, SEM

1. Introduction

In the face of advanced technology the business scenario has become superfluous convoluted, competitive and resultant worldwide organizations recognized that win-win situation is lies within their

intangible assets called talent (Chabault, Hulin & Soparnot, 2012). Talent has considered the predominant currency in today's technological advanced era (Sahai & Srivastava, 2012). The term talent management attained a significant consideration from practitioners and academic worldwide in 1997 just after the introduction of McKinsey consultants "War for Talent" (Axelrod, Handfield-Jones, & Michaels, 2002). Academia has started to evaluate the phenomenon of talent management more closely since last few decades. Researchers considered total talent management is the strategic instrument to obtain a sustainable competitive advantage by a business (Vaiman, Scullion & Collings, 2012), and the future triumph of business linked with business strategy to acquire, motivate and retain the talented candidates of marketplace (Scullion & Collings 2011). Researchers revealed that the core competence of business is their talented employees (Dries 2013), high potential employees have direct correlation with business growth (Collings, 2014). In the walk of globalization Moreover, in today's competitive environment, total talent management has found successive element for sustainable survival (Al Ariss, Cascio & Paauwe 2014).

According to a research survey, 75% of US companies give top priority to talent management, followed by UK found similar results more than 50% of UK organizations concur the success with total talent management (Larsen, 2012). Further supported by researchers study demonstrated that total talent management is a significant element of business success (Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries & Gonzales-Cruz 2013), however, capabilities and skill of talented employees are a sustainable competitive advantage (McDonnell, Hickey & Gunnigle 2011). According to research studies, employers not ignore the impact of talented employees and always give first priority in today knowledge-base-economy for business success (Thunnissen, Boselie & Fruytier, 2013). Total talent management is essential attribute of survival and long term sustainability for business (Gallardo-Gallardo, Dries & Gonzalez-Cruz, 2013). In today globalized era talent management has become the predominant currency for business (Sahai & Srivastava, 2012).

Apropos total talent management is essential for worldwide organizations in order to cater the domestic requirements and compete globally, but very few studies have conducted third world countries to examine the phenomena talent management (Elarabi & Johari 2014; Nafei 2015; Biygautane & Al Yahya, 2014). Further research study reported that no comprehensive study has been undertaken to evaluate talent management phenomena in contexts of Pakistan (Khalique et al., 2015; Shahzad et al., 2016). Further aggravated by today labor market characteristics, sophisticated number of international labor mobility combines with demographic shifting, an aging workforce in developed countries, globalization and technological advancements. Owing to these characteristics of the labor market, a substantial number of skilled Pakistanis, particularly professional individuals such as, doctors, engineers, scientists, IT experts, and managers etc. either fly from Pakistan or they plan to do so. Such a migration trend of talented individual estimated to be dramatically increased in the face of high demand in developed countries with the retirement of baby boomers. The study aims to evaluate the topic of total talent management and identify factors responsible for effective management in the context of Pakistan. This research study is undertaken with aims to determine critical factors of total talent management in the context of Pakistan with expatriates prospective. Study offer strategic level suggestions for domestic organizations to captured sophisticated number of talents.

2. Literature Review

Table 1: Talent Management

Author	Definition
Schweyer (2004)	Talent management is an ongoing process that includes; identify, attract, select, develop and retain high intellectual candidates in the marketplace.
Lewis and Heckman (2006)	Talent management as like as a human resource management process comprised recruitment and selection, motivation, providing growth & development opportunities to talent employees, their retention and success planning.
Hartmann et al. (2010)	Talent management explicitly focused on identification, selection, development, motivation and retention of talented employees.

2.2 Factors Affecting Talent Management

The organizations made investments on application of total talent management practices will definitely receive high productivity as a return. The investment may be in term of talents, motivation will decrease their turnover ratio in order to save cost incurred in talent recruitment, training and development. In literature review session the entire conjunct factors that seems to be responsible for total talent management were critically evaluated and following factors are found that drive more popularity with regard to total talent management; recruitment & selection, remuneration & reward, supply & demand, social & security, technological advancement, career development and workplace environment (Khalique et al., 2015; Shahzad et al., 2016).

2.3 Recruitment and selection & Talent Management

Research study revealed a significant relationship between talent management and fair recruitment & selection processes (Nishad Nawaz 2014) further concludes that an effective talent management system ensured to inboard right candidate for the right job (Ballesteros et al, 2010; Azman, Sirat and Pang, 2016). Researchers conclude that the chief problems arising session of total talent management as the attraction and recruitment of the right candidate (Mpofu & Barkhuizen, 2013). According to the authors, total talent management phenomena play fundamental role in the attraction and selection of high intellectual candidates of marketplace (Davies and Davies 2010; Blass and April 2008; Kirkland 2009). Recruitment & selection have found positive predictor of TM (McDonnell et al. 2010; Dries 2013a; Al Ariss, Cascio & Paauwe 2014). On the basis of aforesaid evidence for this study following is the first hypotheses:

H₁: Recruitment/selection has a substantial influence upon talent management.

2.4 Technology & Talent Management

The study demonstrated technological advancement has positive correlation with organization total talent management practices (Teletov et al., 2017). Further reveal that business sustainability and success is associated with constant development and advanced technology at workstation to enhance productivity & durability to compete in the domestic and global market (Lauzikas et al. 2016; Baroniene, Zirgutis 2016). Advanced technology has found a significant positive impact on total talent management (Crosbie et al. 2017; Mouraud 2017). On the basis of aforesaid evidence for this study following is the second hypotheses:

H₂: Technology has substantial influence upon talent management.

2.5 Demand-Supply & Talent Management

Literature revealed there is a positive correlation amid talent demand & supply ratio (Groves 2011; Moczydlowska 2012). Talent supply and demand ratio greatly contributes within business survival (Schuler et al. 2011). It plays a primary role to ensure the provision of right candidates for the right job and also maintain equilibrium amid talent supply & demand in the market (Cappelli, 2008).

H₃: Demand/supply has substantial influence upon talent management.

2.6 Workplace Environment & Talent Management

Research concludes that favorable work environment has a significant impact on talent satisfaction (McDonnell, 2011; Collings, 2014). Literature revealed that provision of a favorable working environment is robustly linked to talent, productivity (Naharuddin & Sadegi, 2013). Research study demonstrated that favorable attributes of work places have a significant effect on job satisfaction and found a positive relationship amid a conducive working environment and employee satisfaction (Boyce et al., 2013).

H₄: Workplace environment has substantial influence upon talent management

2.7 Social & Security & Talent Management

The authors demonstrate a positive association amid total talent management and job security (Roper, 2009; Gracia, Salanova, Grau & Cifre, 2013). According to Sell and Cleal (2011) social and security attributes have direct relation with talent management. Further concludes a positive significant association amid organizational talent, commitment and social dependency (Bakotic and Babic, 2013; Zahedi et al., 2015). The researcher found a positive correlation amid total talent management and employees social & security attributes (Hassan and Fuadah, 2014).

H₅: Social & security attributes have substantial influence upon talent management

2.8 Remuneration & Talent Management

The study revealed a positive relationship amid application of fair reward system and talent management (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015). Researchers further found the handsome remuneration package and good reward system positive predictor of TM (Shikdar & Das, 2003; Okpara, 2004). Based on above, the following hypotheses has formulated for the study:

H₆: Remuneration has substantial influence upon talent management.

2.9 Career Development and Talent Management

Research study revealed that career development opportunities, reduce turnover and enhance performance of talented employees (Kadiresan et al., 2015). Researchers revealed career development as positive predictor of TM (Price, 2015; Sahai & Srivastava, 2012).

H₇: Career development has substantial influence upon talent management.

2.9 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework was underpinned by the demonstration of context, concepts, and associated factors related research topic.

Table 2: Summary of Theories

Theory	Author(s)	Description
Organizational Support Theory	Eisenberger et al., (1990)	Employee response to their perceptions about how an organization values their contributions, wellbeing and cares
Person- Organization Fit theory	Kimmerle et al., (2008)	This theory is about the cognitive fit of talented individuals with origination environment, structure and citizenship. Working environment and other social / financial attributes being provided by the organization are best fitted to talented individuals.
Social capital Theory	Iles et al. (2010)	This theory emphasizes the role of conducive workplace provided by the organization and responding of talent toward it once they declared as high potential.
Egalitarian (Inclusive) theory	Iles, Chuai, & Preece, (2010)	According to this theory the term talent management inclusive, applicable the management of all employees. In accordance with the theory all employees of are talented or/and have the capabilities to become talented employees if provide opportunities.
Elitist (Exclusive) theory	Iles, Chuai, & Preece, (2010)	According to this theory the term talent management is concerned exclusively the management of only high performer possessed abilities, potential and their segregation due to surpass contribution.

3. Method

3.1 Population

This research study population comprised overseas Pakistani engineers and doctors perusing their professional life in developed countries.

3.2 Sampling

The researcher used snowball sampling technique for data collection from the male and female doctors/ engineers who were working abroad and were citizen of Pakistan.

3.3 Data Collection

Total 300 questionnaires were submitted to overseas Pakistani engineers and doctors working abroad through electronic mail and 251 questionnaires were returned by these overseas Pakistan, rate of

response was 84%. Study participants were found voluntary to take part in the research survey and confidentiality of their responses were assured in all respects. Furthermore the respondents were appraised that the collected data through questionnaire will only be used for research purpose.

3.4 Measures

The measurement scales were adopted from the study of (Sing et al., 2014).

4. Data Analysis

Table 3: Demographics

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	227	90.4
Female	24	9.6
Total	251	100.0
Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Unmarried	220	87.6
Married	31	12.4
Total	251	100.0
Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Engineering	215	89.7
Medical	36	10.3
Total	251	100.0

The above table presents the exact number of participants along with cumulative percentage. The table shows that out of 251, 227 were found male respondents, however only 24 were found female respondents with a percentage ratio of 90.4% and 9.6%. Further depict that 220 were unmarried and only 31 were found married. The percentage ration of unmarried and married were revealed 87.6% and 12.4%. The qualification statistic depicts that 215 respondents belong to engineering, whereas, only 36 respondents were found medical with percentage ratio 89.7% and 10.3%.

Table 4 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Recruitment/Selection	KMO	Bartlett's			Factor Loading								Communality		
		Chi ²	Df	Sig.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8			
1. Item 1	.816	791	15	.000	.67									.571	
2. Item 2					.73										.691
3. Item 3					.78										
Tech Advancement	KMO	Bartlett's			Factor Loading								Communality		
		Chi ²	Df	Sig.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8			
1. Item 1	.871	4503	8	.000	.62									.563	
2. Item 2					.71										.614
3. Item 3					.67										
T. Supply/Demand	KMO	Bartlett's			Factor Loading								Communality		
		Chi ²	Df	Sig.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8			
1. Item 1							.61							.567	

2. Item 2	.916	672	3	.000			.64						.673			
3. Item 3							.74						.718			
W. Environment	KMO	Bartlett's			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Communality			
		<i>Chi²</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>												
1. Item 1	.699	1069	3	.000				.71					.653			
2. Item 2								.73						.675		
3. Item 3								.66						.543		
Security/Social Issues	KMO	Bartlett's											Communality			
		<i>Chi²</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
1. Item 1	.841	3696	3	.000					.81				.634			
2. Item 2								.62					.759			
3. Item 3								.61					.543			
Remuneration System	KMO	Bartlett's											Communality			
		<i>Chi²</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
1. Item 1	.740	2066	25	.000						.73			.727			
2. Item 2											.58			.632		
3. Item 3												.65			.660	
4. Item 4												.61			.653	
5. Item 5												.72			.612	
6. Item 6												.60			.639	
7. Item 7												.63			.610	
8. Item 8												.70			.603	
9. Item 9												.82			.686	
10. Item 10												.72			.510	
Career Advancement	KMO	Bartlett's											Communality			
		<i>Chi²</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
1. Item 1	.718	3662	18	.000							.64		.518			
2. Item 2												.81			.615	
3. Item 3													.62			.634
4. Item 4													.81			.618
5. Item 5													.61			.544
6. Item 6													.65			.765
7. Item 7													.73			.622
Talent Management	KMO	Bartlett's											Communality			
		<i>Chi²</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
1. Item 1	.615	641	3	.000								.75	.612			
2. Item 2													.61		.616	
3. Item 3														.57		.780

The statistical value of the Bartlett's revealed $p < 0.01$ all factors show significant, as per rule of thumb i.e. P value less than or equal 0.05 is significant. The table also stratified the assumption of sphericity clearly highlights that said data is apposite for further analysis. The statistics further show that for 35 items of 8 variables have 34 iterations performed. Subsequently, no item was dropped as the statistic of entire

communalities have been revealed greater than acceptable range, i.e. .50 further strengthened by the statistical value of rotated component matrix show that items have strong loading (Leech et al., 2005).

4.2 CF Analysis

Below mentioned model and table depicts the CFA of eight factors with fit indices. All the indices were found fit (Gaskin & Lim, 2016).

Figure-1 CFA

Table 5: Fit Indices

Models	NFI	AGFI	RMSEA	GFI	RMR	CFI	X ² /df
Normal Value (Uslueletal., 2008)	>.9	>.8	<.08	>.9	<.1	>.9	<.3
Model 7	.91	.82	.07	.94	.01	.92	2.3

Note. X²= chi-sqr, df = degree of freedom, GFI = goodness of fit index, AGFI = Adjusted goodness of fit Index, RMR = root mean error of residuals, RMSEA = root means sqr error of approximation, CFI = comparative fit index, NFI = normed fit index

4.3 Model Validity

Validity statistic of the model (convergent and divergent validity) is underneath.

Table 6: Validity

Variables	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Recruitment/ Selection	0.941	0.844	0.019	1.002	0.919							
2. Tech Advancement	0.993	0.978	0.019	0.993	0.139	0.989						
3. Talent Demand/Supply	0.992	0.978	0.007	1.000	0.041	0.041	0.989					
4. Work Environment	0.963	0.897	0.008	1.005	0.009	0.070	0.085	0.947				
5. Security/Social Issues	0.991	0.974	0.023	1.000	0.015	0.062	0.003	0.090	0.987			
6. Remun & reward Sys	0.986	0.877	0.023	0.997	0.056	0.053	0.012	0.043	0.151	0.937		
7. Career development	0.959	0.770	0.022	0.976	0.026	0.031	0.009	0.060	0.024	0.063	0.944	
8. Talent Management	0.878	0.706	0.021	0.885	0.018	0.044	0.024	0.056	0.029	0.068	1.036	0.954

Note. CR=Composite Reliability, AVE=Average Variance Extracted, MSV=Maximum Shared Variance

The above statistics show that there no evidence of validity concern. Resultantly model is found good to fit according to suggested values (Hu & Bentler, 1999). For validity and good fitted model CR value should be higher than 0.70, AVE higher than 0.50 and MSV should be less than AVE.

4.4 Multiple Regression Analysis

The below model present the analysis

Figure-2 Path Outcome

Table 7: Regression

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
TM	<---	RS	1.645	.009	175.134	***
TM	<---	TA	1.516	.007	221.840	***
TM	<---	SD	.915	.033	28.051	***
TM	<---	WE	2.598	.010	271.428	***
TM	<---	SS	-.362	.010	-37.071	***
TM	<---	RR	-1.219	.012	-104.789	***
TM	<---	CA	-4.072	.011	-363.757	***

Above statistics show that recruitment/selection, advancement in technology talent demand-supply and environment were originates substantial constructive conjecture of TM because their values are ($\beta = 1.6, t = 175.13, p < .05$), ($\beta = 1.5, t = 221.84, p < .05$), ($\beta = .91, t = 28.05, p < .05$) and ($\beta = 2.5, t = 271.42, p < .05$) respectively. Further revealed that, security & remuneration, social issues and rewards system and advancement of career were originated substantial negative conjecture of TM because their values are ($\beta = -.36, t = -37, p < .05$), ($\beta = -1.2, t = -104, p < .05$) and ($\beta = -4.0, t = -363, p < .05$) respectively.

5.1 Discussion

The KMO and Bartlet test statistics satisfied the assumption of sphere city and subsequent data is found suitable for further analysis. Moreover, the computed values of communities were revealed greater than recommended value, i.e. .50 resultantly no single item has been dropped. The statistical finding of factor model is found good fitted because the model has their own significant loadings. Results also confirm no evidence of validity concern and the model has found good fitted in accordance to suggest value (Gaskin & Lim, 2016). The multiple regression analysis, statistics revealed, recruitment & selection have confirmed substantial constructive predictor of TM. The finding of this study is consistent with past research of Vnouckova Lucie, Urbancova, Hana, Smolova, Helena (2016). The technological advancement has revealed a significant positive and result is found consistent with early findings of Pfano and Andrishya Beharry (2016). Supply and demand ratio of talent has revealed significant positive predictor and study finding confirmed the findings of previous study of Cappelli (2008). Study found that work environment is significant positive predictor and study finding is found consistent with early research of Zahedi and Hadadi, (2015). Security and social attributes were found negative predictors. Result is inconsistent with findings of past study conducted by Ahmed et.al., (2017). This study found remuneration and rewards is negative predictor and result of study is inconsistent with findings of past study conducted by Viljoen, Shelley, Ann, (2014). Multiple regression analysis show that career advancement is significant negative predictor of talent management and result is inconsistent with findings of past study conducted by Khurshid, Kashif, Rabbi, Faria, Ali, and Tanzila, (2015). Based on statistical values of multiple regression analysis all the research hypotheses are accepted.

5.2 Findings

Study findings reveal that a) The KMO and Bartlet test statistics satisfied the assumption of sphere city consequently the data is found reliable and appropriate for further analysis. Moreover, the communalities values were revealed greater than recommended value i.e. .50 resultantly no single item has been dropped. b) The statistical finding of factor model is found good fitted because the model have own

significant loadings and questionnaire items were proven valid and good fit, c) the statistical values of multiple regression analysis show that; recruitment & selection, advancement-technological, demand-supply ratio, workplace-environment have significant positive predictors whereas, security-social, rewards-remuneration & advancement-career are the substantial destructive forecaster of talent management.

5.3 Recommendations

Study recommended that a) HEC and degree awarding institute required to ensure quality education, b) Organization must ensure fairly-play in all respect and provides growth and development opportunities to talented employees based on deserving / fair merit, c) providing secure and conducive working environment, d) effectively use media to develop the positive image of the country and organizations, e) HEC required to revamping existing education system and sufficient budget may allocate to education sector, f) government required to support and encouraging talented youth to take initiative/creative programmes and projects for national development, g) workout on establishing such mechanisms to obtain assistant from overseas Pakistanis in all sectors for development and k) the Bureau of emigration and overseas employment along with other associated intergovernmental departments must formulate strategic framework to reverse back the home talent their possibilities and seriously pursues the activities in all respect & level.

5.4 Conclusion

This research was undertaken to evaluate the phenomena of total talent management with aims to identify and measure critical factors of total talent management. Research study focused on overseas Pakistani talent i.e. doctors and engineers perusing professional life in developed country. Based on study findings and review of relevant literature this study found total seven factors significantly contribute in total talent management in Pakistan. These significant factors includes: a) fair recruitment & selection, b) ensure the provision of advanced technology in accordance to contemporary world requirement, c) look-after the social and security attributes of talented employees, d) talent supply & demand ratio, e) provision of conducive working environment to talents, f) provision of growth and development opportunities, g) offering handsome remuneration and fair reward policy. Study result revealed that in the context of Pakistan with expatriates prospective; fair recruitment & selection process, provision of advanced technologic, talent supply & demand ratio, and provision of conducive environment at workstation ascertained significant positive predictors.

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